

OILAVIY TAJRIBANI SHAKILLANTIRISHDA USTOZLARNING TARBIYAVIY VA AHLOQIY JIHATDAGI O‘RNI

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ANNOTATSIYA

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Kalit so‘zlar : oila, oila bu tarbiyaviy maskan

Ustozga hurmat Islom odobidandir , ularga qo‘ldan kelgancha xizmat qilib duolarini olishimiz lozim bo‘ladi. Ustoz xaqqi ota-ona haqqi bilan teng bo‘ladi. Chunki ota-ona farzandini dunyoga kelishiga sababchi bo‘lsa, ustoz esa oxirat binosining tiklanishiga asosiy sababchidir . Ustozga nisbatan cheksiz xurmatda bo‘lmog‘ imiz lozim va ustozni amrini ya’ni qanday xizmati bo‘lsa bajarish lozim. Ustozga kamtarin va iloji bo‘lsa xudbin bo‘lmaslik lozim va zarur ustoz bor joyda ustoz izn bermaguncha betartibsizlik va sabr-toqatsizlik bilan turib ketmaslik kerak. Bu ustozga hurmatsizlikni va gapini mensimaslikni bildirib turadi. Ota kabi ulug‘ va mehribon ustozlarimizni xayrli duosini olish bizlarni yuksak martabaga sazovor bo‘lishimizga asos bo‘ladi. Ustozni izidan borib xayrli duosini olgan odam yuksaladi va balandparvoz martabalarga erishadi. Ustozlar o‘z hayotini ta’lim- tarbiyaga baxshida etadigan fidoiy insondir. Ilm-u ma’rifatga yo‘llovchi qalb gavxariga ziyo nurin tarqatuvchi eng yaqin do‘st va to‘g‘ ri yo‘l ko‘rsatuvchi, mehr va odamiylik bulog‘ i, o‘z kasbini va sohasini zukko bilimdoni adolat va haqiqat timsoli bo‘lgan ustozlar juda katta hurmatga va el-u yurti uchun qilgan xizmatlari uchun ming-minglab tahsinga sazovordirlar.

Mustaqilligimiz tufayli mamlakatimizda ustoz murabbiylarga bo‘lgan e’tibor yanada kuchayib bormoqda. Yurtimizda bugungi kunda ulug‘ va mo‘tabar zot bo‘lgan ustozlarga barcha shart - sharoitlar, o‘z eshigin ochib bormoqda. Bunga misol qilib ustozlarni mehnatini e’zozlash maqsadida har yili 1-oktabrni “O‘qtuvchi va murabbiylar kuni” - umumxalq bayrami sifatida nishonlanishini olsak bo‘ladi. Buyuk mutafakkir Alisher Navoiy bobomiz ulug‘ ustozlarimiz haqida shunday fikr bildirib o‘ tadilar:

Haq yo'lida Kim senga bir hard o'qitmish ranj ila, Aylamak oson emas oning haqqin yuz ganj ila.

Ustozlarni hayot doskasiga yozgan so'zlari hech qachon o'chmaydi. Ulug' va dono ustozlarning iboralari va hikmatli so'zlari yoshlarni tarbiyalab, ularni orzu maqsadlarini amalga oshirishga yordam beradi.

Ahmad Yugnakiy ilmga shunday tarif beradi: - "Ilmsiz inson - misoli iliksiz so'ngak kabidir".

Xalqimizda shunday chiroyli mazmunga ega maqol bor – "Ustoz ko'rmagan shogird har tomonga yo'rg'alar".

Abdulla Avloniy aytganidek, har bir muallimning saodati, davlatimizning tinch-totuv va rohatda yashashida yoshlarning tarbiyasiga bog'liqdir.

Ta'lim - tarbiyaning rivojlanishi tarbiya tizimidagi islohatning muvaffaqiyati ko'p jihatdan o'qtuvchi va murabbiylarga bog'liqdir. Ustoz jamiyat binosining eng ajoyib binokori, ma'rifat bog'ining oliyhimmat bog'bonidir. Ustozlar hayot bo'stonidagi yosh nihollarning baquvvat daraxtga aylanishi uchun beminnat, beqiyos mehnat qiladi. Shuning uchun ham uning shogirdida haqqi benihoya katta va ulug'dir. Ustoz shogirdini o'z farzandi kabi ko'radi, ba'zida esa undanda ziyodroq ko'radi. Shunday ekan, bizga yaxshi tarbiya berib kelayotgan ustozlarga doimo hurmatda bo'lishimiz lozim. Ba'zi bir farzandlar ustozini haqoratlaydi va ustozini bilan muloqot qilganda esa huddi o'z tengquriga muomila qilganday muomila qiladi. Bu esa manmanlik va xudbinlikdir. O'z oilasida tarbiya topa bilmagan farzandni qanay qilib ustozlar tarbiyalaydi. Birinchi Prizdentimiz o'z asarlarida ustoz-murabbiylarga e'tibor kelajakka e'tibor masalasi haqda fikr bildirib o'tgan: - "Yuksak ma'naviyat - yengilmas kuch" asarida ustozlarga shunday ta'rif berilgan: O'z kasbining fidoyilari hisoblangan ustozlarimizning har yili ko'tarinki kayfiyatda nishonlanadigan bayrami haqida quyidagi fikrlarni uchratishimiz mumkin: Bu bayram avvalo, o'zining bilim va tajribasi iste'dodi va mahorati insoniy fazilatlarini, ko'z nuri, qalb qo'ri butun borlig'ini ayamadan, ma'rifat yo'lida betinim xizmat qiladigan ustoz va murabbiylarga nisbatan xalqimizning azaliy hurmat-ehtiromining yaqqol namunasi. Oy Quyoshdan Nur olib borliqni yoritgani kabi shogird ustozidan ziyo olib, hayot ma'shalini yoritadi. Ustozlar aynan millatni ulug'likka yetaklab, insonni yetuk qiladilar va dunyoni yaxshi tomonga o'zgartiradilar.

Har bir sohada bo'lgani kabi tajribasiz, ilmsiz yoki saviyasiz ustozlarimiz yo'q emas albatta. Tajribasiz ustozda bo'lmagan fazilatlar dono va oqil ustozlarda bor. Yaxshi ustoz jamiyatni chiroyli qilib tuzatsa, fe'li yomoni va ilmi sayozi esa o'sha

jamiyatni buzadi, borini ham yo‘qqa chiqaradi. Yaxshi va tajribali ustoz o‘z kasbiga ilmga bo‘lgan mehrini oshirib yoshlarga yaxshi axloqiy tarbiya bersa, tajribasiz va ilmsizi esa uni batamom yo‘q qilib yuboradi. Saviyasiz ustozlar qo‘lida ta’lim-tarbiya olgan shogirtning ertasi jinoyatchi, buzg‘ unchi desak mubolag‘ a bo‘lmaydi. Bunday ustozlarning jamiyatda ko‘payishi esa kelajakda boshimizga nelarni solishi mumkinligini o‘ylashga qo‘rqasan kishi...

Ustoz otangdek ulug‘ naqlida bir dunyo ustozga bo‘lgan samimiy ehtirom namoyondir. Ustozlarimiz, vatanimizni gullab yashnashi uchun o‘z hissasini qo‘shibgina qolmasdan el-yurt ardog‘ idagi aziz inson bo‘lishga harakat qiladi. Ustozimiz murg‘ ak paytimizdayoq qalbimizga ezgulik urug‘ ini sochadi, qo‘limizdan tutib, ma’rifat sabog‘ ini beradi va dillarimizga mehr-muhabbat ulashadi. Biz erishayotgan yutuqlarimiz va qo‘lga kiritayotgan g‘ alabalarimiz kim tufayli? - Albatta ustozlarimiz tufaylidir . O‘sha g‘ alabalarimizda ota – onamiz qatori ustozlarimizni o‘rni va hissasi benihoya kattadir . Shunday ekan ularni mudom ardoqlab hamisha sharafshimiz kerak. Bizni qalbimizda sizdek yoshi ulug‘ , munis va mo‘tabar ustozlarning borlig‘ i o‘zgacha faxr va iftixor ila tilga olamiz. Ana shuni o‘zi ham o‘zgacha baxt emasmi, ustoz yaxshi tinglovchi, ba’zida esa qalbimizga malham berguvchi shifobaxsh da’vo hamdir .

Translation into english

The educational and moral role of teachers in shaping family experience

Respect for the Master is an Islamic etiquette, and we must serve them as best we can and receive their blessings. The teacher’s fee is equal to the parent’s fee. Because if the parent is the cause of the birth of the child, the teacher is the main cause for the restoration of the building of the hereafter. We must have infinite respect for the Master and obey the Master’s command, that is, whatever service he has. The teacher should not be humble and selfish if possible, and should not stand in chaos and impatience until the teacher gives permission where there is a necessary teacher. It signifies disrespect and disregard for the teacher. Receiving the blessings of our great and loving teachers, such as the Father, is the basis for our success. He who follows in the footsteps of the Master and receives his blessings will rise and attain lofty careers. Teachers are dedicated people who dedicate their lives to education. Justice and truth teachers who are emblems deserve great respect and thousands of praises for their services to the country.

Due to our independence, the attention to teachers in our country is growing. In our country today, all the conditions for teachers, who are great and respected, are

opening their doors. An example of this is the fact that every year on October 1, Teachers 'and Coaches' Day is celebrated as a national holiday in honor of the work of teachers. The great thinker Alisher Navoi said the following about our great teachers:

Who is on the path of truth with a hard-hearted resentment, It is not easy to turn around with his true face.

The words that teachers wrote on the board of life will never fade. The sayings and wise sayings of great and wise teachers help nurture young people and help them achieve their dream goals.

Ahmad Yugnaki describes science as follows:

There is a proverb among our people that has such a beautiful meaning - "A student who has not seen a teacher walks in all directions."

As Abdullah Avloni said, the happiness of every teacher depends on the education of young people in the peaceful and prosperous life of our state.

The development of education The success of the reform of the education system depends in many ways on teachers and educators. The Master is the most magnificent builder of the community building, the noble gardener of the Garden of Enlightenment. Teachers work tirelessly to turn the young saplings in the garden of life into a vigorous tree. That is why the right of his disciple is so great and great. The teacher sees the student as his own child, and sometimes more so. Therefore, we should always respect the teachers who have been giving us a good upbringing. Some children insult their teacher and treat their teacher as if they were their peers. This is arrogance and selfishness. How do teachers raise a child who cannot be raised in their own family? In his works, the First President commented on the issue of attention to the future of teachers: - In the book "High spirituality is an invincible force" teachers are described as follows: We can find the following thoughts about the holiday, which is celebrated in a good mood in the year: My face is a clear example of the eternal respect of our people for the teachers and coaches who serve me. Just as the Moon brings Light from the Sun to illuminate the universe, so the student receives light from the Master and illuminates the torch of life. It is the teachers who lead the nation to greatness, mature man, and change the world for the better.

Of course, we do not have teachers without experience, knowledge or level, as in any field. Qualities that are not present in an inexperienced teacher are present in wise and prudent teachers. When a good teacher makes a society beautiful, his bad deeds and shallow knowledge destroy that society and destroy everything. A good and experienced teacher will increase the love of his profession for science and give young

people a good moral upbringing, while an inexperienced and ignorant person will completely destroy it. It is no exaggeration to say that a student who is educated by low-level teachers is a criminal and a spoiler. And the increase in the number of such teachers in the society makes one afraid to think about what might happen to us in the future.

The teacher is a great tribute to your father, a world of sincere respect for the teacher. Our teachers not only contribute to the prosperity of our country, but also strive to be a dear person in the honor of the people. Our Master sows the seeds of goodness in our hearts, holds our hands, teaches us enlightenment, and shares love in our hearts. Who is to blame for our successes and victories? - Of course, thanks to our teachers. The role and contribution of our teachers, as well as our parents, in those victories is enormous. Therefore, we should always honor and respect them. We speak with special pride and pride that we have in our hearts such old, munis and respected teachers as you. Isn't that a blessing in disguise, a healing claim that a teacher is a good listener, and sometimes an ointment to our hearts.

FOYDALANGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YHATI: (REFERENCES)

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